

Investigation of electrical properties of solid polymer electrolyte based on bio-degradable poly(vinyl pyrrolidone) polymer

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Abstract : Solid polymer electrolytes consisting of poly(vinyl pyrrolidone) (PVP) as host polymer and ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) as doping salt have been prepared by solution casting technique using dimethyl sulphoxide as solvent and characterized for electrical properties. The XRD analysis shows the increase in amorphous nature and the FT-IR analysis confirms the complexation behaviour of the polymer electrolytes. The AC impedance analysis indicates the increase in ionic conductivity of the electrolyte as the concentration of NH₄Cl increases. The maximum conductivity has been found to be 1.495×10^{-5} S cm⁻¹ at 303 K for 80 mol% PVP : 20 mol% NH₄Cl. The temperature dependent conductivity obeys Arrhenius law. The dielectric properties have been discussed.

Keywords : Polymer electrolyte, XRD, FTIR, ionic conductivity.

Introduction

Solid polymer electrolytes are promising materials as electrolytes in solid state ionic devices. In recent years, considerable progress has been made to enhance the electrical conductivity, electrochemical and mechanical stability of these polymer electrolyte materials to be utilized for various applications like solid state batteries, fuel cells, sensors, electro chromic display devices, etc.¹. Many polymers such as poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO)², poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA)³, poly(*N*-vinyl pyrrolidone) (PVP)⁴ and polymer blends like PVP/Chitosan^{5,6} and PVA/PVP^{7,8}, etc. have been used as host materials and several inorganic acids, lithium salts and ammonium salts have been used as dopants for the preparation of solid polymer electrolytes. Among the various vinyl polymers, poly(*N*-vinylpyrrolidone) (PVP) is a biodegradable polymer possessing good environmental stability, easy processability, moderate electrical conductivity and rich physics in charge transport mechanism. Addition of ammonium salts to PVP has a marked influence on the conductivity of the polymer electrolyte^{9,10}. Hence, in the present work, thin films of polymer electrolytes consisting of PVP as host polymer and ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) as doping salt have been prepared in various compositions by solution

casting technique using dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent and characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) and AC impedance spectroscopy techniques.

Experimental

Appropriate quantities of PVP ($M_w = 40,000$, Sd Fine Chem. Limited) and NH₄Cl (Spectrum) in different compositions (in mol%) of 100 : 0, 95 : 5, 90 : 10, 85 : 15 and 80 : 20 are dissolved in DMSO and stirred well until homogeneous solutions are obtained. Then these solutions are poured into poly propylene petri dishes and kept in a vacuum oven at 70 °C for 6 days for complete solvent evaporation. The thickness of the prepared polymer electrolyte films has been found to be in the range of 0.0056–0.01448 cm.

XRD patterns of the films are recorded at room temperature with a Philip's X'Pert PRO diffractometer and Cu K α radiation. FT-IR spectroscopy studies are carried out at room temperature using a Shimadzu-IR Affinity-1 Spectrophotometer in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹. The electrical conductivity and dielectric studies are carried out on the films with aluminium blocking electrodes using a HIOKI 3532 LCZ meter of frequency range 42 Hz–1

MHz in the temperature range 303–343 K.

Results and discussion

XRD studies :

Fig. 1(a-d) represents the XRD pattern of pure PVP and different compositions of PVP-NH₄Cl polymer electrolytes. Two broad peaks observed at 12.2° and 22.4° from Fig. 1(a) reveal the amorphous nature of pure PVP⁴. On addition of NH₄Cl, the broadness and the relative intensity of these peaks are found to be increased and decreased, respectively as evidenced from the XRD pattern, Fig. 1(b-d), of PVP doped with salt which indicates the increase in amorphous nature of PVP. The polymer electrolyte with 20 mol% NH₄Cl has been found to be more amorphous. The increase in the amorphous nature causes a reduction in the energy barrier to the segmental motion of the polymer electrolyte. Presence of peaks at $2\theta = 32.82^\circ, 52.97^\circ, 58.5^\circ, 23.19^\circ$ and 47.05° (JCPDS file No. 34-0710) corresponding to NH₄Cl in the polymer-salt complexes indicates the incomplete dissociation of the salt in the polymer matrix.

Fig. 1. (a-d) XRD pattern of pure PVP and different compositions of PVP-NH₄Cl polymer electrolytes.

FTIR studies :

On addition of the salt into the polymer host, the cation of the salt is expected to coordinate with the polar groups in the host polymer matrix resulting in the complexation. This type of interaction will influence the local structure of the polymer backbone and certain infrared active modes of vibration will be affected³.

FTIR spectra of pure PVP and PVP-salt complexes are shown in Fig. 2(a-c). The absorption peak at 2137

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of (a) pure PVP, (b) 15 mol% and (c) 20 mol% NH₄Cl doped PVP.

cm⁻¹ attributed to C-N stretching of pure PVP is shifted to 2133 cm⁻¹ in 85 mol% PVP-15 mol% NH₄Cl and 2140 cm⁻¹ in 80 mol% PVP-20 mol% NH₄Cl. The band at 1690 cm⁻¹ corresponding to carbonyl group, C=O of pure PVP is displaced to 1682 cm⁻¹ and 1700 cm⁻¹, respectively in 15 mol% and 20 mol% salt-doped systems¹¹. The band at 1440 cm⁻¹ assigned to CH₂ wagging of pure PVP gets shifted to 1458 cm⁻¹ and 1474 cm⁻¹ in the polymer electrolytes. The band at 2854 cm⁻¹ corresponding to CH₂ stretching of pure PVP is shifted to 2870 cm⁻¹ and 2825 cm⁻¹, respectively, in 15 mol% and 20 mol% NH₄Cl-doped samples. The band of pure PVP around 1024 cm⁻¹ attributed to C-C stretching vibrations is shifted to 1018 cm⁻¹ and 1026 cm⁻¹, respectively, in the polymer with 15 mol% and 20 mol% NH₄Cl. Moreover, a peak present at 1497 cm⁻¹ in PVP is found to be absent in the PVP doped with NH₄Cl. In addition, a new peak appears at 1875 cm⁻¹ and 1902 cm⁻¹ respectively in the samples with 15 mol% and 20 mol% NH₄Cl. The shifting may be due to the interaction of the dissociated salt with the polymer matrix. These results indicate the complex formation between the polymer and the salt.

Conductivity studies :

Fig. 3 depicts the conductance plots for different compositions of PVP-NH₄Cl polymer electrolytes at 303 K. The plots consist of a low frequency dispersion region relating to the blocking of ions between the electrodes and the electrolyte, frequency independent plateau region in the mid frequency corresponding to the bulk conductivity of the electrolytes and high frequency dispersion region in which the conductivity increases with angular

frequency obeying Jonscher's power law¹² represented by,

$$\sigma(\omega) = \sigma_{dc} + A\omega^n$$

where σ_{dc} is the dc conductivity, A and n are temperature dependent parameters. The dc conductivity values have been calculated by the extrapolation of the plateau region to zero frequency. The maximum ionic conductivity has been found to be $1.495 \times 10^{-5} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ at 303 K for 80 mol% PVP-20 mol% NH_4Cl polymer electrolyte in the concentration range studied. The σ_{dc} values for different compositions of PVP- NH_4Cl polymer complexes at different temperatures have been presented in Table 1 which clearly shows that the ionic conductivity increases with increase in NH_4Cl concentration. This may be due to build-up of charge carriers and also to the increase in the amorphous nature of the polymer electrolyte which reduces the energy barrier thereby facilitating the ion transport.

Fig. 3. Variation of conductivity for all PVP- NH_4Cl polymer electrolytes at 303 K.

Fig. 4 shows the variation of ionic conductivity as a function of inverse temperature for the polymer electrolytes with different NH_4Cl content. It can be seen from the Fig. 4 that the curves are almost linear with regres-

Fig. 4. Variation of conductivity with inverse temperature for PVP- NH_4Cl polymer electrolytes.

sion values close to unity suggesting the Arrhenius type motion of ions represented by,

$$\sigma T = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT),$$

where σ_0 is the pre-exponential factor, E_a , the activation energy and T , the absolute temperature and k , the Boltzmann constant. It has been observed that the dc conductivity of all the samples is enhanced with increase of temperature. When the temperature is increased, the mobility of polymer chain is enhanced, and fraction of free volume in the polymer electrolyte system increases accordingly, which facilitates the translational motion of ions. The segmental motion either allows the ions to hop from one site to another site or provides a pathway for ions to move. Hence, the ionic motion in the polymer electrolyte is due to hopping of ions from one site to another site and the dynamic segmental motion of the polymer, which leads to an increase in the ionic conductivity¹³. The activation energy for ion transport for all the prepared samples calculated from the Arrhenius plots are presented in Table 1. It is seen that the sample with 20 mol% NH_4Cl has low activation energy (0.60 eV).

Dielectric spectra analysis :

The dielectric behavior of a material is described by

Table 1. Conductivity values for PVP- NH_4Cl polymer electrolytes at different temperatures

PVP- NH_4Cl (mol%)	dc conductivity, σ_{dc} (S cm^{-1})					Activation energy, E_a (eV)	Regression value
	303 K	313 K	323 K	333 K	343 K		
95 : 5	1.807×10^{-8}	6.170×10^{-7}	2.548×10^{-6}	8.575×10^{-6}	2.548×10^{-5}	1.55	0.925
90 : 10	1.131×10^{-6}	4.850×10^{-6}	9.458×10^{-6}	3.587×10^{-5}	4.864×10^{-5}	0.857	0.964
85 : 15	4.010×10^{-6}	7.178×10^{-6}	2.358×10^{-5}	5.609×10^{-5}	1.152×10^{-4}	0.785	0.986
80 : 20	1.495×10^{-5}	2.762×10^{-5}	5.947×10^{-5}	1.212×10^{-4}	2.028×10^{-4}	0.600	0.996

Fig. 5. Variation of ϵ' with frequency for (a) different concentrations of PVP-NH₄Cl at 303 K and (b) 80 mol% PVP-20 mol% NH₄Cl at different temperatures.

the complex permittivity :

$$\epsilon^* = \epsilon'(\omega) - j\epsilon''(\omega)$$

where real $\epsilon'(\omega)$ and imaginary $\epsilon''(\omega)$ components are the storage and loss of energy in each cycle of the applied electric field¹⁴. Fig. 5(a) and (b) shows the variation of dielectric constant, $\epsilon'(\omega)$ with frequency for different concentrations of PVP-NH₄Cl at 303 K and for 80 mol% PVP-20 mol% NH₄Cl at different temperatures.

High values of $\epsilon'(\omega)$ at low frequency may be due to the interfacial effects within the bulk of the sample and the electrode effects¹⁵. The inability of the charge carriers to orient themselves in the field direction at higher frequencies results in the decrease in dielectric constant¹⁶. Also, the ϵ' value is found to increase with increasing concentration of NH₄Cl indicating an increase in charge carrier density and hence the increase in conductivity¹⁷. The dielectric constant increases at higher temperatures due to the higher charge carrier density.

As temperature increases, the degree of salt dissociation and redissociation of ion aggregates increases resulting in the increase in number of free ions.

Conclusion

Solid polymer electrolytes with various compositions of PVP and NH₄Cl have been prepared by solution casting technique using the solvent DMSO and characterized by XRD, FTIR and AC impedance techniques. The increase in amorphous nature and the interaction between the polymer and the salt and hence the complex formation between them have been confirmed by XRD and

FTIR studies, respectively. The conductivity is found to exhibit increasing trend with increasing salt concentration in the concentration range studied. The highest room temperature conductivity has been obtained for 80 mol% PVP-20 mol% NH₄Cl and it is found to be 1.495×10^{-5} S cm⁻¹. The variation of conductivity with temperature for all the electrolytes follows Arrhenius equation in the temperature range measured. The activation energy for ion conduction seems to decrease with the addition of NH₄Cl content. The highest conducting sample (80 mol% PVP-20 mol% NH₄Cl) has low activation energy (0.6 eV). The low frequency dispersion observed in the dielectric spectra implies the space charge effects arising from the electrodes.

References

1. F. M. Gray, "Solid Polymer Electrolytes : Fundamentals and Technological Applications", Wiley VCH, New York, 1991.
2. A. Chandra, P. C. Srivastava and S. Chandra, *J. Mat. Sci.*, 1995, **30**, 3633.
3. M. Hema, S. Selvasekarapandian, D. Arunkumar, A. Sakunthala and H. Nithya, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 2009, **355**, 84.
4. C. S. Ramya, S. Selvasekarapandian, G. Hirankumar, T. Savitha and P. C. Angelo, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 2008, **354**, 1494.
5. M. H. Buraidah and A. K. Arof, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 2011, **357**, 3261.
6. M. F. Z. Kadir, Z. Aspanut, S. R. Majid and A. K. Arof, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A : Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 2011, **78**, 1068.
7. N. Rajeswari, S. Selvasekarapandian, S. Karthikeyan, H.

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- Nithya and C. Sanjeeviraja, *Int. J. Polym. Mater.*, 2012, **61**, 1164.
8. Natarajan Rajeswari, Subramanian Selvasekarapandian, Moni Prabu, Shunmugavel Karthikeyan and C. Sanjeeviraja, *Bull. Mater. Sci.*, 2013, **36**, 333.
9. N. Vijaya, Subramanian Selvasekarapandian, G. Hirankumar S. Karthikeyan, H. Nithya, C. S. Ramya and M. Prabu, *Ionics*, 2012, **18**, 91.
10. Naranappa Vijaya, Subramaniyan Selvasekarapandian, Shunmugavel Karthikeyan, Moni Prabu, Natarajan Rajeswari and Chinnappa Sanjeeviraja, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2013, **127**, 1538.
11. Rajarshi Bhattacharya, T. N. Phaniraj and D. Shailaja, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 2003, **227**, 23.
12. A. K. Jonscher, *Nature*, 1977, **267**, 673.
13. W. Zhu, X. Wang, B. Yang and X. Tang, *J. Polym. Sci. B : Polym. Phys.*, 2001, **39**, 1246.
14. P. Dutta and S. Biswas, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2002, **37**, 193.
15. S. Ramesh, A. H. Yahava and A. K. Arof, *Solid State Ionics*, 2002, **152-153**, 291.
16. K. Adachi and O. Urakawa, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 2002, **307-310**, 667.
17. J. R. MacCallum and C. A. Vincent, "Polymer Electrolyte Reviews", Springer, 1989, **2**, 43.